

AAE59000MAAC Week2 reading report

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Abstract—This article constructs a unified framework and model for multi-agent consensus and collaboration, and conducts discussions and analyses in both continuous-time and discrete-time dimensions. At the same time, many possible application scopes were also discussed, such as the management and allocation of objects in space, the analysis of networks in group theory, and their application in distributed control systems, etc. Overall, this article summarizes and outlines the basic consensus in the mathematical models and algorithmic results of multi-agent systems, discusses the performance of the algorithms and the speed at which consensus is achieved, thereby enabling us to have a comprehensive and holistic understanding of consensus. Subsequently, I also conducted a basic analysis and modeling of the team coordination on the football field based on some of the ideas presented in the article.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

A. Introduction

1) *Key problem*: The article first defined the concept of "consensus", and then, starting from the most basic definition of "consensus", discussed some related issues. If we abstract the connections of a multi-agent system into a graph, the structure of the graph will determine the performance and possibilities of our consensus.

When will our system be able to reach consensus? How fast can it achieve consensus? What is the value of the consensus? Can it still be achieved in the presence of real-world interference (time-delay)? These are all the issues that were discussed and argued about in this context.

2) *Unified 'description method' and perspective*: Firstly, we abstract the multi-agent system into a connected graph, where the nodes in the graph have directional connections, which represents the information transmission in the original system. Subsequently, the article presents a fundamental algorithm, which transforms the key steps necessary to reach consensus into a Laplacian matrix L .

$$\dot{x} = -Lx$$

B. Motivation

The practical system requires a universal mathematical model first, which can help us describe and express the problems we are facing. Secondly, we need abstract mathematical methods, which also facilitate our qualitative analysis of the system's performance in reaching consensus in the future. At the same time, the article also takes into account the real-world factors and describes the system's performance under external disturbances and undesirable conditions.

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II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Basic setting

Consider the network with n agents and we can use a graph $G(V, E)$ to represent. Each node $i \in V$ have a state which we write it as x_i .

The agent i can only obtain the information of its neighboring nodes (other agents) which represent as \mathcal{N}_i . The neighbor set of each intelligent agent is determined by the connection pattern of the multi-agent system. In other words, it is determined by the structure of the graph and the flow of information.

Our goal is to change the state of each intelligent agent by controlling the input, and finally make the states of all intelligent agents $x_i(t)$ reach a unified value x , thereby achieving the goal of consensus.

This means:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x_i(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x_j(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} x_k(t) = x, \forall i, j, k \in V. \quad (1)$$

This is the basic definition of the ultimate goal: consensus that we have come up with. So how can we achieve the ultimate goal of reaching consensus? This requires us to adjust the agent system step by step based on its own and its neighbors' states. We will discuss them separately in terms of continuous states and discrete states.

B. Protocol to achieve consensus

1) *Continuous time*: We achieve the final consensus by controlling the changes in our own states.

$$\dot{x}(t) = -Lx(t), \quad (2)$$

where

$$x = [x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n]^T,$$

At this point, in the system, L can be understood as the weight of each multi-agent's current state corresponding to the decision of its neighbors to change their states. In the graph, we can regard it as the graph Laplacian.

2) *Discrete time*: In discrete-time systems, at this point we can describe the update of the state as:

$$x(k+1) = Px(k), \quad (3)$$

where P is a nonnegative row-stochastic matrix related to the Laplacian (e.g., $P = I - \epsilon L$ with some adjustable step size.)

III. MAIN RESULTS

Overall, the article summarizes and describes the performance and results of reaching consensus under this algorithm, analyzes the convergence of the system, the analysis of the consensus value and convergence speed achieved, the factors determining the speed at which the system reaches the final state, the robustness of the system, and the stability analysis in the presence of delay in information transmission between multiple agents (nodes). Moreover, by using the knowledge and basic properties of graph theory and matrix theory, the universality and feasibility of this algorithm and protocol are demonstrated.

A. Result 1: Consensus conditions and final consensus value

Under our algorithm, we can ultimately achieve the effect of consensus. This requires a 'Laplacian' matrix with a similar negative feedback mechanism to achieve the final consensus and consistency. For connected non-directed graphs, consensus can eventually be reached. And the result of the algorithm indicates that the final consensus value is the average of all the initial values of the states.

For an undirected graph, the final consensus value x_f

$$x_f = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^k x_i(0), \forall i, j \in V, \quad (4)$$

At this point, we can draw the conclusion that for unidirectional-connected graphs (multi-agent systems without a clear direction of information flow), the final value of the consensus is determined by the initial values of each agent.

B. Result 2: Undirected connected graph - Using Laplacian matrix

In the analysis of undirected graphs, the article presents another explanation method. The paper utilizes the sum-of-squares property of the Laplacian.

$$x^\top Lx = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} a_{ij} (x_j - x_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

And for an unbalanced system

$$\phi(x) = \frac{1}{2} x^\top Lx \quad (6)$$

We can observe that the fundamental principle of the algorithm for achieving consensus is similar to the gradient descent algorithm in optimization. Or, from the perspective of control theory, we can interpret this way of achieving consensus as a PD controller. At the same time, this algorithm, like these other interpretations, also has similar properties and results.

C. Result 3: Analysis of the performance of convergence speed

Finally, we discovered that the speed at which the system reaches consensus depends on a certain eigenvalue of the Laplacian matrix L in the system. We find that the second smallest eigenvalue λ_2 of this matrix determines the rate of convergence.

We found that the second smallest eigenvalue λ_2 of L in the

system is larger, the convergence speed of the system is faster. And we can call λ_2 as the algebraic connectivity.

Therefore, we can observe that the convergence speed performance of the system is determined by one of the eigenvalues of the Laplacian matrix. If we understand it from the perspective of the graph, we will find that the convergence speed of the system is determined by the spectral properties of the topology of the graph composed of nodes.

D. Result 4: The case when the system is a 'directed graph'

For a strongly connected directed graph (digraph), the paper states a key result (Theorem 1):

If the Laplacian matrix L admits a positive left eigenvector ξ such that

$$\xi^\top L = 0,$$

then:

- 1) The agents still achieve asymptotic consensus.
- 2) The consensus value is not the simple average, but a weighted average:

$$\alpha = f(z) = \frac{\xi^\top z}{\xi^\top \mathbf{1}} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i z_i, \quad w_i = \frac{\xi_i}{\sum_k \xi_k}.$$

- 3) If the digraph is *balanced* (for each node, total in-weight equals total out-weight), then $\xi = \mathbf{1}$, and the result reduces to average consensus:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i(0).$$

So we can notice that for both undirected and directed graph, our manner can achieve the consensus at last, and the final consensus values are the mean, the difference between them is the calculation method. For a strongly connected directed graph, the final consensus value will be the weighted average of the initial values, and this weight depends on the number of input information at this node.

E. Result 5: Switching (Dynamic Topology) Result

The paper models the time-varying topology as a switching system:

$$\dot{x} = -L(G_k)x, \quad k = s(t).$$

In the paper it clarify the theorem 5: If every digraph in the set $\{G_k\}$ is balanced and strongly connected, define

$$\lambda_2^* = \min_k \lambda_2(G_k).$$

Then, for any switching signal $s(t)$, the system achieves *average consensus*, and the convergence rate is no slower than λ_2^* .

This result is very significant because it indicates that this algorithm has certain robustness. In a switching network, we do not need to limit the switching frequency and change speed of the system. Secondly, there is a so-called lower limit for the convergence speed of our system, which enables us to have an estimate of the speed and performance at which this system reaches consensus. We can also anticipate the worst-case scenario, and in the worst case, the average consensus can still be achieved in the end.

F. More result: play with some application

For the average consensus algorithm with time delay, the paper states: The sufficient condition for convergence is constrained by the maximum degree, and is summarized as "the larger the maximum degree, the more intolerant to time delay", with a clear trade-off. The paper directly states: Scale-free networks with hubs are more vulnerable to time delay, while random graphs and small-world networks are relatively more robust. Therefore, engineering networks should not blindly construct extremely high-degree nodes.

IV. YOUR THOUGHTS ON FURTHER RESEARCH

I am a football fan. I believe the research on multi-agent consensus has given me a new perspective to understand the stories on the football field, and also enabled me to approach problems from the coach's viewpoint.

However, due to the vastness of the football field, we will discuss it from a more specific aspect. This time, we will attempt to understand and describe what happens on the football field by adjusting the concept of "consensus".

The reason why it is possible to combine the dynamic choices of players on the field with the consensus algorithm of multi-agent systems is that there are strong commonalities between them: players can communicate with each other, just like the definition of the neighbor set in a multi-agent system, which enables the transmission of information, thus allowing us to understand the tactical execution of the team and the dynamic state of the players from the perspective of distributed control. However, at the same time, on the real field, coaches or leaders on the court also have the authority and ability of a commander, so to some extent, the operation of the team is carried out through the coordination of distributed and centralized control. Later, if I have time, I can study it in detail.

A. Basic setting

Position $p(t)$ We define the position of a player on the field as a two-dimensional function, which will be regarded as a description of the specific position of that player.

$$p_i(t) \in \mathcal{R}^2, i \in [1, 11] \quad (7)$$

However, we need to be aware of one issue. There is no distinction of superiority or inferiority regarding the positions of players on the field. Due to the different divisions on the field, each player needs to choose the optimal position based on the tactical requirements and the limitations of their role. Let's assume that the positioning choices of a team are clear. Then, here we are more inclined to focus on the changes in the positions of the players. In other words, the dynamic movement of the players on the field is more worthy of attention.

Movement $m(t)$ We define the movement function of the player as the first derivative of the position function. At this point, the meaning of the movement function encompasses two dimensions, but we only use its absolute speed (without direction).

$$m(t) \in \mathcal{R}, i \in [1, 11], \quad (8)$$

$$m(t) = |\dot{x}(t)| = \sqrt{\left(\frac{dx(t)}{dt_x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dy(t)}{dt_y}\right)^2}, \quad (9)$$

So at this point, the movement function is an objective description of the players' movement speed on the field.

Direction $d(t)$ Now let's define the direction function. This can be understood as the direction in which the player's body is facing, or it can be regarded as the movement function of the player, indicating the direction in which they will move in the next moment. The direction function can be understood as the direction in which the car's front is pointing. This does not mean that the car will definitely move in this direction in the next second, but it at least shows the forward trajectory of the object's speed at this moment.

$$d_i(t) \in \mathcal{R}, i \in [1, 11], |d(t)| \in [0, 2\pi], \quad (10)$$

To provide a more intuitive explanation, the following figures will vividly illustrate the actual performance forms of each function on the sports field.

Fig. 1. Figure 1: $p(t)$: The display of a player's position, and the change in position $m(t)$ represents the trajectory.

Fig. 2. Figure 2: $m(t)$

B. Creation of the status of player

1) *State Vector of Each Player*: We have already defined:

- $p_i(t) = [x_i(t), y_i(t)]^\top \in [-1, 1]^2$,
- $m_i(t) = \|\dot{p}_i(t)\|$,
- $d_i(t) = \text{atan2}(\dot{y}_i(t), \dot{x}_i(t)) \in [0, 2\pi)$.

The state of player i is defined as

$$s_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_i(t) \\ y_i(t) \\ m_i(t) \\ d_i(t) \\ r_i(t) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Here, $r_i(t)$ denotes the *tactical/role state*, used to represent a player's strategic tendency at the team-policy level (e.g., more offensive vs. more defensive).

At this point, the tactical inclination of the players is of great significance, because the goal of the game is to win. Each of our players has a certain role to play. Every team and every coach will make special and targeted divisions for different players for each game. And only when different players reach a consensus can it be considered the consensus of the entire team.

2) *Definition and description of tactical/character status*:

$$r_i(t) \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}.$$

For example:

- 1 = Defender,
- 2 = Midfielder,
- 3 = Forward,
- 4 = Goalkeeper (optional).

Our process is similar to assigning 'numbers' to players based on their roles on the field. The advantage of this approach is that we can view what happens on the field from the perspective of a 'manager' or coach, and we can effectively categorize it. However, we must also be aware that in the real game, the responsibilities of the players may shift and mix, which is increasingly occurring in modern football and coaching theories. The current state setting that we are making is very idealized.

3) *Another option Continuous "Role Weight/Tendency"*:

$$r_i(t) \in [0, 1].$$

This can be interpreted as an *offensive tendency*:

- $r_i = 0$: fully defensive,
- $r_i = 1$: fully offensive,
- $0 < r_i < 1$: balanced / midfield-like.

The advantage of this description method lies in the fact that the continuous variables we create will be more conducive to our mathematical operations in all aspects. For instance, we can perform differentiation of states or perform additions at the decimal level.

C. Our goal

First of all, we clearly define our selection criteria for the players' tactical performance status $r(t)$.

We will employ continuous state variables to describe the tactical roles of the players on the field. Secondly, at this point we will first assume that the consensus we expect the team to reach is a formation consensus. Not everyone converges to a single point, but rather gathers into "the same formation shape/formation manifold".

However, we also need to pay attention to the players' own status $s(t)$, such as the rhythm (speed), the direction of advancement, and the tactical inclination, which should be coordinated (it can be "the same" or "following the same instructions of the entire team").

Now, let's construct our simple mathematical model based on our set goals and the consensus objectives.

D. Model for State Definition and Consensus Objectives

a) *Player state definition (with continuous tactical tendency)*.: Consider a team of n players indexed by $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ moving on a normalized field $[-1, 1]^2$. The position of player i is

$$p_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_i(t) \\ y_i(t) \end{bmatrix} \in [-1, 1]^2. \quad (11)$$

Following the previously defined kinematic quantities, the (absolute) speed magnitude is

$$m_i(t) = \|\dot{p}_i(t)\| = \sqrt{\dot{x}_i(t)^2 + \dot{y}_i(t)^2}, \quad (12)$$

For each player's movement on the field, we represent the player's body orientation and movement status on the field by defining the movement function that determines the speed of the movement and the direction function that defines the direction of the player's body.

And the moving direction is represented by the unit direction vector

$$u_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos d_i(t) \\ \sin d_i(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad d_i(t) = \text{atan}(\dot{y}_i(t), \dot{x}_i(t)) \in [0, 2\pi), \quad (13)$$

where $u_i(t)$ is used in the consensus formulation to avoid the angle discontinuity at 0 and 2π . To incorporate a coach-level tactical interpretation, introduce a continuous "offensive tendency"

$$r_i(t) \in [0, 1], \quad (14)$$

where $r_i(t) \approx 0$ indicates a defensive tendency and $r_i(t) \approx 1$ indicates an offensive tendency. The overall player state is then defined as

$$s_i(t) = \begin{bmatrix} p_i(t) \\ m_i(t) \\ u_i(t) \\ r_i(t) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6. \quad (15)$$

b) *Main objective: formation consensus (shape unification)*.: The primary objective is not to collapse all players to a single point (aggregation), but to achieve a unified formation

shape. Let the tactical tendency modulate a desired formation offset through a mapping

$$q_i(t) = Q(r_i(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (16)$$

where $Q(\cdot)$ encodes how a player's tactical role shifts the target region on the field.

We can also interpret $Q(t)$ as the deviation between the actual position of this player and his theoretical ideal position under the coach's tactical intentions. In order to reach consensus, this player should move according to the 'instructions' of $Q(t)$. And depending on the coach's tactical choices and the player's own tactical definitions, each player's movement target will be different.

Define the *formation-normalized position*

$$z_i(t) = p_i(t) - q_i(t). \quad (17)$$

$z(t)$ is the difference between the actual positions of the team's players and the ideal positions of the players. Or, this function represents the direction and speed of movement that the players should undertake.

By doing this, we can ignore the players' positions and only consider the positions each player chooses after disregarding their tactical positioning. In this way, we can better focus on the changes in the team formation and the consistency of the overall movement.

Formation consensus is defined as

$$\|z_i(t) - z_j(t)\| \rightarrow 0, \quad \forall i, j, \quad (18)$$

which implies that, asymptotically, all players share a

Fig. 3. Figure 3: $z(t)$: The convergence of $z(t)$ mean consensus.

common translational component $c(t)$ while preserving role-dependent offsets:

$$p_i(t) = c(t) + q_i(t) + o(1). \quad (19)$$

For a communication graph $G = (V, E)$ with nonnegative weights a_{ij} on edges $(i, j) \in E$, a convenient scalar measure of formation disagreement is

$$E_{\text{form}}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} a_{ij} \|z_i(t) - z_j(t)\|^2. \quad (20)$$

Thus, $E_{\text{form}}(t) \rightarrow 0$ quantifies convergence toward a unified formation.

Fig. 4. Figure 5: The gap between the player's current position and the ideal position

c) 3) Auxiliary objectives: consensus of kinematic and tactical states.: In addition to formation unification, it is desirable that the team exhibits coherent behavior in speed, direction, and tactical tendency. Using the same graph weights a_{ij} , define the following disagreement energies:

$$E_m(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} a_{ij} (m_i(t) - m_j(t))^2, \quad (21)$$

$$E_u(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} a_{ij} \|u_i(t) - u_j(t)\|^2, \quad (22)$$

$$E_r(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} a_{ij} (r_i(t) - r_j(t))^2. \quad (23)$$

Here, $E_m(t) \rightarrow 0$ indicates a synchronized movement tempo, $E_u(t) \rightarrow 0$ indicates alignment of instantaneous moving directions, and $E_r(t) \rightarrow 0$ indicates convergence to a common tactical tendency across the team.

At this point, we have broken down the overall goal of our team's consensus. The "consensus" of the rhythm represents the intensity of the game that the team should maintain. The consistency of this intensity is of utmost importance. For instance: In a game, it cannot be the case that only the forwards are desperately pressing the opponent while the defenders remain unmoved. Such uniformity is also very important for the distribution of players' physical strength. The "consensus" of direction indicates that the team is unified in terms of ball control or the advancement strategy of the formation. Sometimes it requires a collective rush to press the opponent, and sometimes it requires positioning

for defense. This ensures the compactness of the formation. While the "consensus" of tactics represents that each player can understand and attempt to execute the tactical intentions of the team's "brain". The "consensus" of tactics is the highest level of "consensus".

Fig. 5. Figure 4: $E(t)$: The energy need to achieve consensus.

Alternatively, if a coach-level command $\rho(t) \in [0, 1]$ is assumed (e.g., the team is instructed to shift from defensive to offensive), the tactical objective can be written as a tracking term

$$E_\rho(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i(t) - \rho(t))^2, \quad (24)$$

which emphasizes coordinated adaptation to a shared global strategy rather than identical pairwise agreement.

d) 4) *Unified objective.*: A compact team-level objective that prioritizes formation consensus while simultaneously encouraging coherent kinematic and tactical behavior is

$$J(t) = E_{\text{form}}(t) + \alpha E_m(t) + \beta E_u(t) + \gamma E_r(t), \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma > 0, \quad (25)$$

or, when a coach command $\rho(t)$ is adopted,

$$J(t) = E_{\text{form}}(t) + \alpha E_m(t) + \beta E_u(t) + \gamma E_\rho(t), \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma > 0. \quad (26)$$

In this formulation, $E_{\text{form}}(t)$ is the primary term ensuring formation shape unification, while $E_m(t)$, $E_u(t)$, and $E_r(t)$ (or $E_\rho(t)$) serve as auxiliary terms that promote team-level coordination in movement tempo, heading, and tactical tendency.

V. MY NEXT STEP FOR MY OWN IDEA

A. Summary for my idea

I hope to utilize the knowledge of "consensus" presented in this article to understand and even shape the models of many sports that require teamwork, in an attempt to understand the specific ways in which consensus is achieved in our actual sports scenarios.

I chose to analyze football because the system on the football field has many similarities to the analysis of multi-agent systems. Each player on the field can be regarded as an intelligent agent, and on the tactical board, each player is often regarded as a node. There is communication and information transmission between them, which enables the application of the consensus prerequisite in many multi-agent

systems. This allows many feasible algorithms to be used.

I conducted an analysis and modeling of the coordination among various players on the football field based on the basic physical characteristics of the field. We defined the dynamic changes and states of the players on the field, and we also divided the tactical responsibilities of different players according to the different tactics. Because on the field, the consensus is that players with different roles and characteristics work together in a coordinated manner.

At this point, the definition and understanding of "consensus" become interesting. This time, I will only describe this issue from a very limited and narrow perspective: the compactness of the formation.

In any sport, a compact formation and a good physical condition are both crucial. Not only on the football field, but also in team sports such as basketball, rugby, ice hockey, etc., maintaining an appropriate distance between team members and maintaining the correct body orientation are very beneficial for achieving the team's goals.

I have divided this current consensus into three aspects: speed, direction of advancement, and tactical coordination. I believe these three aspects - the on-field strategies, the rhythm, and the players' willpower - can describe the current consensus goal. Moreover, we can weight these three aspects and construct a target function. This can even be transformed into an optimal control problem.

B. Problem description and my understanding for the possible way to solve it

Now the question arises: How can we ensure that the players can reach consensus in the aforementioned three aspects? This requires us to have a plan and control over every aspect of the players' performance, such as their body positioning, movement speed, and so on.

Secondly, is the currently existing consensus algorithm still applicable at this point? We need to take into account the particularities of football matches: teams have the goal of winning, there are limitations on the players' physical abilities, there are limitations on the players' ability to convey information and the speed and potential limitations of information exchange, there is interference from the opposing players, and there are changes in the players' own mental states, etc.

Finally, what exactly was the effect of the coach's instructions and on-the-spot adjustments? I believe this is the key issue here. If we compare a team to a system, then the coach and the team's spiritual leader are the two core controllers for the players' tactical understanding and their mental states. In other words, the coach's instructions to the players can be regarded as the control input of the controller, and the strategy specified by the coach before the game is the control rate that the team reaches a consensus on in various game situations. This is of utmost importance, as it indicates that if we follow the content of this article

$$\dot{x} = -Lx$$

The coach's actions will affect the Laplacian matrix. In other words, the coach is also a part of this system.

C. How to solve it

Then how should I solve this problem? Good question! I'm also thinking about it. Perhaps I can look for the answer in graph theory and topology. Since the spectral properties of the Laplacian matrix determine the convergence and consensus performance of the system, and the coach's behavior $\rho(t)$ is itself a part of the Laplacian matrix, then we can combine the coach's input and the team's form to construct the team's Laplacian matrix, and thereby analyze the impact of the coach's tactics and the players' states on the overallity and collaboration ability of the team.

This is my next goal: to use the basic tactics of a coach, obtain the expression function of the coach's tactics input, and analyze the impact of this strategy on the compactness of the team formation and the overall consensus.

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